

Household Consumption Pattern and its Impact on Inequality in India: A Post-Globalization Scenario

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Abstract—*The paper intends to analysis household consumption pattern and its impact on inequality in rural and urban sectors after reform period (1993–94 to 2011–12). This study is mainly based on secondary data from different National Sample Survey Office (NSSO) round (50th, 55th, 61th, 66th, 68th) of 'Level and Pattern of Consumer Expenditure' and time period has been taken since 1993–94 to 2011–12. The NSSO provides clear evidence of the downwards trends in share of food expenditure and increase the share of non-food expenditure in total consumption expenditure during this time period. The main finding of paper is 'Cereals and cereals substitute' consumption expenditure has declined around from 24 per cent to 12 per cent in rural sector and 12 per cent to 7.5 per cent in urban sector since 1993–94 to 2011–12. The combined share of pulses, milk, meat, vegetables and fruit etc. has declined about 27.7 per cent to 26 per cent and 29 per cent to 21 per cent in rural and urban respectively. The coarse cereals consumption (kg) has declined about 71 per cent in rural sector and 64 per cent in urban sector over the same period. The inequality has increased in most of states in rural and urban areas. The share of consumption expenditure bottom 30 per cent has declined and top 30 per cent people has increased in rural and urban sectors. The Gini Coefficient has increased 0.280 to 0.302 and 0.340 to 0.379 in rural and urban sectors respectively since 1993–94 to 2011–12. The situation in urban sector has worsened rather than rural areas over the 18 years.*

Keywords: *Consumption Pattern, Food Expenditure, Non-food Expenditure, Inequality, Gini Coefficient*

INTRODUCTION

Indian economy is one of the fastest growing economies in the world at recent years. The growth rate of GDP grew annual by 8.5 per cent since 2004–05 to 2010 as well as annual per capita GDP also increased at 6.5 per cent during the same period (Rangarajan Expert Group Report, 2014). But share of food expenditure in total consumption expenditure has declined as well as calorie intake also decline during post-reform period. It makes puzzle among researchers and policy makers to understand as to why calorie intake has declined when monthly per capita consumption expenditure has increased in real term. Although, NSSO data shows absolute per capita food expenditure has increased since 1987–88 despite lower growth rate poverty was decreased in nineties. Yet, per head calorie intake is decreasing and three quarters of country's population lives below 2,400 Kcal per day per person in rural area and 2,100 Kcal per day per person in urban area (Patnaik, 2013). The main reason of decline calorie intake is that per capita cereals consumption continuously decreases in both rural and urban areas.

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India is third largest economy in the purchasing power parity (PPP) at the world level (Varadharajan and Thomas, 2013). However, the share of food consumption expenditure in total consumption expenditure is declining continuously whereas the share of non- food expenditure is increasing (NSSO 68th Rounds). This observation fits in Engel's law that shows the expenditure on food items decreased due to people's disposable income increased. National sample survey office (NSSO) provides a clear evidence of the downward trend in share of food in total consumption (Economic Survey, 2012), but India became self-reliance in food-grain production after green revolution therefore, availability of cereals like wheat, rice has increased. The objective of study to analyze to change in food basket after reform period and another objective is to measure consumption inequality with help of Gini Coefficient.

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) report-2011 pointed out that inequalities have risen after 1990s when the Indian economy opened its doors to global economies. According to the report, inequalities in salaries earning have risen by two fold over the last two decades. The richer are getting richer and the poorer are getting poorer. The top 10 per cent of wage earners make 12 times more than the bottom 10 per cent, compared to six times from the 1990s. Thus, the growth of nineties could not reduce poverty and inequality. Indian policymakers have always tried to reduce poverty and inequality. After independence, India adopted a development strategy which could reduce inequality and poverty in society. In the early 1990s, the Indian government adopted market-oriented economic reform policies and gave emphasis on liberalization, privatization and globalization. The National Sample Survey Organization data (NSSO 68th Round) shows clear evidence that after liberalization; consumption inequality has increased in both rural and urban sectors. The Indian Human Development Report (IHDI 2001) shows that the Gini coefficient's value increased from 1983 to 1999–2000. The Planning Commission has also accepted that the income inequities has increased since 2004–05; it is that period when the Indian economy has achieved second position in rapid GDP growth in the world after China, According to the Planning Commission data book, the Gini coefficient increased from 0.27 to 0.28 in rural area from 2004–05 to 2009–10 and in urban area, it increased from 0.35 to 0.39.

FOOD GRAINS AVAILABILITY

Agriculture sector was dominant sector and its share in GDP was 57.2 per cent in 1950–51 but after that its share continuously decline and reached 13.9 per cent in 2012–13 (Mishra and Puri, 2014). India imports food grains from other countries to feed its people just after independence but early 70's it apply new policy for agriculture. This strategy was known as green revolution which was commonly characterized as High- Yielding Varieties Programme (HYVP), and after that production and productivity had increased multiple times. On account of India became self-reliance in food grains production.

Table 1.1: Per Person Per Day Availability of Foodgrains (1970 to 2012)

Year	Cereals (Grams)	Pulses (Grams)	Total (Grams)	Edible Oil (Grams)	Vanaspatti (Grams)	Sugar (Grams)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1970	403.1	51.9	455	3.5	1	7.4
1980	379.5	30.9	410.4	3.8	1.2	7.3
1990	435.3	41.1	476.4	5.5	1	12.7
2000	422.7	31.8	454.4	8.2	1.3	15.8
2010	401.7	35.4	437.1	13.1	1.1	18.6
2011	410.6	43	453.6	13	1	17
2012	408.6	41.7	450.3	13.8	1	18.7

Source: Economic Survey 2011–12.

Although, Per capita food availability has increased (Table 1.1) but the share of food expenditure decreased in total consumption along time as well as nutritional intake also declined specially during the post reform period. The important food basket like cereals, pulses, edible oil sugar and it's per person per day availability has shown since 1970 to 2012. The total per capita per day cereals availability is about 403 grams in 1970 and it has reached 408 grams in 2012. The Table 1.1 also shows per person per day pulses availability has declined from 1970 to 2012. The important point to mention is that per capita total cereals (cereals and pulses) have declined from 455 grams to 450 grams and edible oil has continuously increased 3.5 to 13.8 grams per day per person. The same observations can be seen that per capita sugar availability has increased from 7 grams to 18.7 grams during the same period.

CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE: PRE-AND POST-REFORM PERIOD

Consumption expenditure data has been taken from different quinquennial surveys of NSSO since 1972–73 to 2011–12. (27th round, 32nd round, 38th round, 43rd round, 50th round, 55th round, 61st round, 66th round, and 68th round and that's time period is 1972–73, 1977–78, 1983, 1987–88, 1993–94, 1999–2000, 2004–05, 2009–10 and 2011–12 respectively. Consumption expenditure pattern of household in pre and post reform period has been shown in Table 1.2. The Following table reflects the food consumption expenditure decline at slow rate during pre-reform period but after reforms consumption expenditure has drastically changed and the share of non-food expenditure has increased more rapidly in total private consumption expenditure.

Table 1.2: Share of Consumption Expenditure on Food and Non Food Items: Pre and Post Reform Period (1972–73 to 2011–12)

Sr. No. Item	Pre Reform Period				Post Reform Period				
	1972–73	1977–78	1983	1987–88	1993–94	1999–2000	2004–05	2009–10	2011–12
Food expenditure	68.7	62.15	62.35	60.2	58.95	53.75	48.75	47.15	43.55
Non-food expenditure	31.3	37.85	37.65	39.8	41.05	46.25	51.25	52.85	56.45
Total expenditure	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: NSSO 43rd round 1993–94 and NSSO 68th Round.

In pre reform period, food consumption expenditure share has declined around 68 to 60 per cent in total consumption expenditure from 1972–73 to 1987–88 whereas share of non-food expenditure has increased about 31 to 40 per cent in total consumption expenditure over the same period. Non -food consumption expenditure has increased rapidly during post reforms, whereas share of food expenditure has been decreased continuously during the period 1993–94 to 2011–12. According to Table 1.2, Food consumption expenditure has decreased around 59 per cent to 43 per cent. On the other hand non-food expenditure has increased from 41 per cent to 56 per cent over the period 1993–94 to 2011–12. The data significantly fits in Engel's law proving that higher the disposable income lower will be the share of food expenditure as consumption basket shift food to non-food item

It is important to analyze that why consumption expenditure shifts in consumption expenditure from food to non-food in past. Often, the argument is in support of it, as we adopted new economic policy in July 1991. There are several structural changes; Indian economy opened its door to world economy and an era of globalization commenced. The role of government has been limited now and the role of private sector has increased forwarding towards more of market economy. Therefore, employment opportunity has increased in private sector which has also increased per capita income after post reform period, consequently consumption basket has been shifted from food to non-food items. Now, consumer spent their income on luxuries goods, durable goods, education, medical care and entertainment and so on. Numerous studies argued that this is due to occupational and structural changes which have increased nonfood items.

It is noticeable that India's population is not getting adequate food and nutritional intake. According to International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), "India's rank is 66th out of 88 in Global Hunger Index (2008)", it shows that India's condition has been extremely poor in Global Hunger Index (GHI). The three indicators used to measure the GHI viz. child malnutrition, rates of child mortality, and the proportion of calorie deficient. IFPRI published Reports (2014) on the proportion of hungry people which has been declined in India has got 55th rank out of 76 countries.

FOOD BASKET STRUCTURE IN RURAL AND URBAN SECTOR

The proportion of food expenditure has declined in during the last four decades (both in rural and urban sector). The share of food expenditure is much higher in total consumption in rural area as compared to urban area (NSSO 68th Rounds, 2011–12). The share of food consumption expenditure has declined in total consumption expenditure around 63 per cent to 48 per cent in rural area and 54 per cent to 38 per cent in urban area during the period 1993–94 to 2011–12. The share of cereals and cereals substitute has also declined around 24 to 12 per cent in rural area and 14 to 7.5 per cent in urban areas over the 18 years period. The combined food expenditure share in pulses, milk, edible oil, meat, vegetable etc. has been declined from 28.7 per

cent to 26.3 per cent in rural sector and in urban sector it is declined about to 28.8 per cent to 21 per cent over the same period. The share of other food expenditure has almost same in rural and urban sector during the period. The decline in consumption expenditure on the food items is mainly due to the high rate of inflation on cereals, as well as cereal consumption replacement by other food items. There has been a decline in cereals consumption and mainly among the middle and high income groups.

Table 1.3: Percentage Share of Food Expenditure in Different Rounds: 1993–94 to 2011–12

Item	Rural Sector				Urban Sector			
	50 th	55 th	61 th	68 th	50 th	55 th	61 th	68 th
Cereals & cereals Substitutes	24.5	22.4	18.2	12.3	14.3	12.5	10.2	7.5
Share of Pulses, Milk, Edible Oil, Meat, Egg, Fish, Vegetables, Fruits & Nuts.	28.7	27.5	27.5	26.3	28.8	25.2	22.9	21.1
Share of Other Food expenditure in total consumption expenditure	10	9.6	9.4	10	11.6	10.2	9.4	10
Total Food expenditure	63.2	59.4	55	48.6	54.7	48.1	42.5	38.5
Total Non-food expenditure	36.8	40.6	45	51.4	45.3	51.9	57.5	61.5
Total consumption expenditure	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Different NSSO Rounds, (1993–94 to 2011–12)

TRENDS IN QUANTITY OF CEREALS AND PULSES CONSUMED PER CAPITA: ALL INDIA

An important point to be noted here (Table 1.4) is that, per capita rice, wheat, coarse cereals, total cereals and pulses has declined over the 18 years in rural and urban area, excepts in wheat consumption which is increased 0.03 kg in rural sector since 1993–91 to 2011–12. During this period the percentage of total cereals has declined about 16 per cent and 12 per cent in rural and urban sector respectively. In case of coarse cereals it has declined about 71 per cent and 64 per cent respectively in rural and urban sectors since 1993–94 to 2011–12. In Indian context, we can conclude that coarse cereals are treated as “Giffen Goods” because of increase income coarse cereals demand has decreased over the same period. In the case of “Giffen goods” case as the price increases demand also increases, and when the price decreases demand also decreases. This is contrary to the fundamental law of demand, which tells that quantity demand for a product decreases as the price increases.

Table 1.4: Per Capita Cereals and Pulses Consumption Over 30 Days

Sector	Rural				Urban			
	1993–94	2011–12	Changes (kg)	Per cent Changes	1993–94	2011–12	Changes (kg)	Per cent Changes
Rice	7.02	6.13	-0.89	-12.68	5.28	4.66	-0.62	-11.74
Wheat	4.40	4.43	0.03	0.68	4.72	4.32	-0.40	-8.47
Coarse Cereals	1.97	0.57	-1.40	-71.07	0.64	0.23	-0.41	-64.06
Total Cereals	13.39	11.22	-2.17	-16.21	10.64	9.28	-1.36	-12.78
Pulses	0.76	0.74	-0.02	-2.63	0.86	0.85	-0.01	-1.16

Source: Author Calculation from NSSO 50th and 68th Rounds

The share of rice has declined about 12 per cent in rural sector and 11 per cent in urban sector since 1993–94 to 2011–12. Pulses are the important sources of

protein which is essential for human growth. The per capita consumption of pulses (kg) has also declined in both rural and urban sector since 1993–94 to 2011–12. The share of pulses has declined from 2.63 per cent to 1.16 per cent in rural and urban sectors over the 18 years in India.

TRENDS AND PATTERN IN MONTHLY PER CAPITA EXPENDITURE (MPCE)

The per capita expenditure data is used for estimation of living standard of population. Per capita consumption expenditure data is measured on monthly basis by NSSO. Monthly per capita income expenditure is obtained by household monthly consumer expenditure divided by household size. Basically, NSSO collects data in two sets, first is Category -1 items “last 30 days” and “last 365 days” and category II and III in only last 30 days. Thus, the household monthly per capita expenditure is measuring in two ways since 1993–94. The first measure of MPCE is called MPCEURP (Uniform Reference Period MPCE) and the second, MPCEMRP (Mixed Reference Period MPCE) and Modified Mixed Recall Period (MMRP) for 2009–10 and 2011–12.

MPCEURP is the measure of MPCE used by the NSS Consumer Expenditure survey (CES) when household consumer expenditure on each item is recorded for a reference period of “last 30 days”. MPCEMRP is the measure of MPCE used by the CES when household consumer expenditure on items of clothing and bedding, footwear, education, institutional medical care, and durable goods is recorded for a reference period of “last 365 days”, and expenditure on all other items is recorded with a reference period of “last 30 days”. MMRP collects the household expenditure data from (1) 7-days for edible oil, egg, fish and meat, vegetables, fruits, spices, beverages, processed food, pan, tobacco and intoxicants, (2) 30-days for the remaining food items, fuel and light, miscellaneous goods and services including non-institutional medical, and rents and (3) 365-days for clothing, footwear, education, institutional medical care, and durable goods.

MONTHLY PER CAPITA EXPENDITURE IN CONSTANT PRICE

Monthly per capita expenditure is better indicator to measure welfare of human being. In India, there is continuous increase in nominal and real term since 1993–94 to 2011–12. To measure real monthly per capita expenditure for rural area and urban India, we have taken Consumer Price Index Agriculture Labor (CPIAL) and Consumer Price Index for Industrial Workers (CPIIW) with price deflator at 1987–88 bases respectively. Table 1.5 shows real MPCE for rural sector has increased around 38 per cent whereas in urban sector it is increased by about 51 per cent over last 18 year respectively.

Monthly per capita expenditure in current prices has been shown in Table 1.5. In rural sector it has been increased from ` 281 to ` 1278 during the period 1993–94 to 2011–12 respectively. In urban sector monthly per capita expenditure has increased from ` 458 to ` 2400 from over the 18 years.

Table 1.5: Change in MPCEURP at Current and Constant Prices (1993–94, All-India in Rs.)

Year	1993–94	1999–2000	2004–05	2009–10	2011–12
Rural Sector					
Rural: MPCE current price	281.4	486.16	558.78	927.7	1278.94
Price Deflator	176	271	319	494	580
Constant Prices 1987–88	159.89	179.39	175.17	187.79	220.51
Urban Sector					
Urban: MPCE: (`)current prices	458.04	854.92	1052.36	1785.81	2399.24
Price Deflator	173	279	338	503	599
Constant Prices 1987–88	264.76	306.92	311.35	355.03	400.54

Source: NSSO 68th Round, 2011–12. #

Note: Price Deflator is calculated for rural sector with the CPI-AL and for the urban sector price Deflator CPI-IW with base year 1987–88=100.

CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE: A BETTER INDICATOR TO MEASURE INEQUALITY

Generally, the per capita income is not measured correctly in developing nations. Per capita income measurement in developing countries is difficult (Hassett and Mathur, 2012). A number of reasons can be given against this. First, it is difficult to measure price estimate to consumer. Second, a small number of households have a regular source of income but most of people have irregular incomes. Government employees and the business sector get a regular income but in agriculture and allied sectors workers' salaries depend on season or have an annual income. Third, reason is that the consumption expenditure provides more useful information in comparison with income. In the previous stage of life, income may be low but it increases with age. Usually, it is expected that in the early age of life, individuals borrow from others but are able to save at later ages. Hence, consumption expenditure is a better measure to calculate inequality. Besides, numerous government policies support to increase consumption expenditure for low income groups.

DECILE CLASS OF MPCE_{URP}: ALL-INDIA

Table 1.6: Decile Class of MPCE_{URP}: All-India in Rs.

MPCE in URP	1993–94		1999–2000		2004–05		2009–10		2011–12	
	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
0–10	115.525	154.18	216.4	291.45	226.665	323.895	377.06	521.32	504.935	706.735
10–20	152.89	210.8	278.69	389.14	296.64	441.32	495.82	722.31	663.47	978.5
20–30	177.55	247.51	321.04	463.92	342.4	533.24	575.69	869.62	773.81	1192.04
30–40	200.01	286.84	360.83	537.22	387.72	625.83	649.25	1027.93	876.19	1400.87
40–50	222.1	331.57	399.9	618.61	432.06	730.17	724.02	1207.69	976.58	1632.16
50–60	249.45	380.72	445.49	718.67	481.55	858	808.34	1420.07	1099.82	1907.49
60–70	281.52	447.58	496.74	840.53	543.25	1014.27	910.15	1687.74	1248.53	2245.74
70–80	324.94	543.46	566.62	1009.67	630.4	1226.39	1053.3	2051.45	1451.73	2729.81
80–90	398.3	698.33	686	1286.19	775	1594.41	1288.78	2680.52	1785.61	3562.57
90–100	686.33	1283.22	1098.17	2383.215	1478.255	3196.425	2394.66	5673.16	3408.77	7636.92

Source: Author calculation from different quinquennial NSS Rounds.

The average decile class of MPCE_{URP} is shown in Table 1.6. The average MPCE has increased for all decile classes in rural and urban sectors at current prices from 1993–94 to 2011–12. If we talk about 2011–12, the 10 per cent bottom population

average MPCE in rural sectors was only ₹ 504 and in urban sector, was ₹ 706. Around one-half of rural population (50 per cent) lives below average MPCE ₹ 976. On the other hand about 10 per cent top average MPCE in rural population holds around ₹ 3408. In urban area, 10 per cent bottom population average MPCE was around only ₹ 706 and top 10 per cent urban population average MPCE was ₹ 7636 as well as 50 per cent population average MPCE only ₹ 1632.

INEQUALITY IN CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE: ALL INDIA

Inequality in consumption expenditure has increased in both rural and urban sectors after the reform period. Table 1.7 shows the share of consumption expenditure of bottom 30 per cent and top 30 per cent of the population in rural and urban sectors during the period 1993–94 to 2011–12.

Table 1.7: Consumption Expenditure Inequality (1993–94 to 2011–12)

Sectors	Rural			Urban		
	Percentage Share in Consumption Expenditure			Percentage Share in Consumption Expenditure		
Year	Gini Coefficient	Bottom 30 per cent Population	Top 30 per cent Population	Gini Coefficient	Bottom 30 per cent Population	Top 30 per cent Population
1993–94	0.280	15.87	50.18	0.340	13.36	55.08
1999–00	0.256	16.76	48.27	0.348	13.40	54.80
2004–05	0.396	15.48	51.55	0.367	12.31	57.07
2009–10	0.291	15.61	51.06	0.382	11.83	58.25
20011–12	0.302	15.19	51.97	0.379	11.99	58.06

Source: Author's Calculation for different quinquennial NSS Rounds.

Fig. 1.3: Gini Coefficient for All India (1993–94 to 2011–12)

Source: Based on Table 1.7

The percentages share of consumption expenditure of bottom 30 per cent population has declined from 15.87 to 15.19 and top 30 per cent consumption expenditure class has increased from 50.18 to 51.97 per cent in rural sector over the past 18 years. The situation in the urban sector has worsened as compared with the rural sector. The percentage share of consumption expenditure of the bottom 30 per cent population in urban sectors has declined from 13.36 to 11.99 whereas consumption expenditure of top 30 per cent has increased from 55 to 58 per cent

during 1993–94 to 2011–12. Figure 1.1 shows inequality has increased in both rural and urban area over a period of 18 years in India. Gini Coefficient has increased in both rural and urban area. It has increased from 0.280 to 0.302 in the rural sector and 0.340 to 0.379 in urban area from 1993–94 to 2011–12. It indicates that the poor are getting poorer and the richer are getting richer.

INEQUALITY IN CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE IN ADVANCED STATES

In advanced states, inequality in consumption expenditure measure with the help of Gini Coefficient. It has increased in rural sector in most of the States such as Gujarat, Kerala, Punjab, Karnataka and Delhi and declined in Haryana, Maharashtra and Tamil Nadu in comparison of 1993–94 with 2011–12. Table 1.8 shows the maximum increase in Gini value has been in Kerala in the rural sector over the past 18 years. In the urban sector, the inequality (Gini Coefficient) has increased in all advanced states except for Tamil Nadu during 1993–94 to 2011–12. Consumption expenditure inequality also declined in Goa from 0.294 to 0.270 in urban area during 2004–05 to 2011–12. The maximum inequality increase in urban, consumption expenditure in the value of Gini Coefficient is in Karnataka followed by Kerala and Haryana.

Table 1.8: Gini Coefficient in Advanced Region (1993–94 to 2011–12)

Advanced States	Rural Sector				
	1993–94	1999–00	2004–05	2009–10	2011–12
Gujarat	0.236	0.234	0.269	0.253	0.282
Haryana	0.301	0.239	0.322	0.301	0.271
Kerala	0.288	0.27	0.341	0.417	0.429
Maharashtra	0.302	0.258	0.308	0.268	0.292
Punjab	0.265	0.239	0.279	0.288	0.301
Tamil Nadu	0.307	0.279	0.316	0.264	0.297
Karnataka	0.266	0.241	0.263	0.235	0.321
Goa	NA	NA	0.294	0.214	0.27
Delhi	0.236	0.294	0.264	0.253	0.262
All India	0.282	0.26	0.3	0.291	0.307
	Urban Sector				
Gujarat	0.287	0.286	0.305	0.328	0.29
Haryana	0.28	0.287	0.36	0.36	0.401
Kerala	0.338	0.321	0.4	0.498	0.436
Maharashtra	0.351	0.348	0.372	0.41	0.366
Punjab	0.276	0.29	0.393	0.371	0.333
Tamil Nadu	0.344	0.381	0.356	0.32	0.334
Karnataka	0.315	0.323	0.364	0.334	0.445
Goa	NA	NA	0.405	0.406	0.291
Delhi	0.207	0.343	0.329	0.345	0.371
All India	0.34	0.342	0.371	0.382	0.385

Source: Planning Commission website and NSSO 68th Round, 2011–12.

INEQUALITY IN CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE IN BACKWARD STATES

Inequality in consumption expenditure at backward states has been shown in Table 1.9.

Table 1.9: Gini Coefficient in Backward States during (1993–94 to 2011–12).

States	Gini Coefficient				
	Rural Sector				
Backward Region	1993–94	1999–2000	2004–05	2009–10	2011–12
Bihar	0.222	0.207	0.205	0.226	0.232
Jharkhand			0.225	0.24	0.231
Uttar Pradesh	0.278	0.246	0.286	0.356	0.265
Madhya Pradesh	0.277	0.242	0.265	0.292	0.283
Chhattisgarh	NA	NA	0.295	0.291	0.277
Odisha	0.243	0.244	0.281	0.262	0.255
Rajasthan	0.26	0.209	0.246	0.225	0.257
West Bengal	0.251	0.224	0.27	0.239	0.257
All India	0.282	0.26	0.3	0.291	0.307
	Urban Sector				
Bihar	0.307	0.319	0.33	0.332	0.297
Jharkhand	NA	NA	0.351	0.358	0.387
Uttar Pradesh	0.323	0.328	0.366	0.329	0.423
Madhya Pradesh	0.327	0.315	0.393	0.364	0.407
Chhattisgarh	NA	NA	0.434	0.326	0.387
Odisha	0.304	0.292	0.35	0.389	0.358
Rajasthan	0.29	0.282	0.367	0.378	0.333
West Bengal	0.334	0.341	0.378	0.384	0.406
All India	0.34	0.342	0.371	0.382	0.385

Source: Planning Commission website (accessed on February 3, 2015) and NSSO 68th Round.

Study found that Gini Coefficient has increased in Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha and Rajasthan during 1993–94 to 2011–12. The inequality in rural sector in backward states is less in comparison with advanced states. The value of Gini Coefficient exists 0.22 to 0.28 in rural sectors in backward states. If we talk about the urban sector, the maximum value of Gini Coefficient is in Uttar Pradesh followed by Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Rajasthan and West Bengal and has declined only in Bihar.

CONCLUSION

Changes in the patterns of consumption expenditure is a complex process, yet, some expensive trends can be identified on the basis of trends and pattern of consumption expenditure in rural and urban sectors over the 18 years in India. In this study we have considered that per capita food expenditure has declined and non-food expenditure has been increased in total consumption expenditure (in both rural and urban sectors) since 1972–73 to 2011–12. During post-reform period, consumption pattern has been rapidly shifted towards non-food items. Cereals and cereals substitute both have continuously declined both pre and post reform period, its share in before reform period. Cereals and cereals substitute consumption expenditure has declined around from 24 per cent to 12 per cent in rural and 14 per cent to 7.5 per cent in urban sector during 1993–94 to 2011–12. The combined share of pulses, milk, meat, vegetables and fruit etc. has declined about 27.7 per cent to 26 per cent and 29 per cent to 21 per cent in rural and urban sectors respectively over the 18 years. The per capita cereals and pulses consumption (kg) has declined

in both rural and urban sector since 1993–94 to 2011–12. The coarse cereals consumption (kg) has declined about 71 per cent in rural sector and 64 per cent in urban sector over the 18 years. Therefore, in Indian context, we can say that coarse cereals are treated as “Giffen Goods”. Real Monthly Per Capita Expenditure (MPCE) in Uniform Reference Period (URP) has increased about 38 per cent in rural sector and 51 per cent in urban sector since 1993–94 to 2011–12.

The deeper analyzing the NSSO consumption expenditure data from 1993–94 to 2011–12, it is found that inequality condition of most of the States is being dangerous. The 10 per cent bottom population average MPCE in rural sector was only ₹504 and On the other hand about 10 per cent top average MPCE in rural population holds around ₹3408. In urban area, 10 per cent bottom population average MPCE was around only ₹706 and top 10 per cent urban population average MPCE was ₹7636 as well as 50 per cent population average MPCE only ₹1632. It is also observed that the share of consumption expenditure of bottom 30 per cent of the people has declined in rural and urban sectors. On the contrary the share of consumption expenditure of top 30 per cent of the people has increased in both rural and urban sector. It is observed that inequality has increased in consumption expenditure in both rural and urban sectors. The value of Gini Coefficient has increased from 0.280 to 0.302 in rural sector and 0.340 to 0.379 in urban sector during the period 1993–94 to 2011–12. The inequality situation in the urban sector has worsened rather than in rural area over the past 18 years. Inequality in consumption expenditure has increased both in the advanced and the backward states in terms of Gini Coefficient.

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